

Benefits of Organic farming for Farmers and Environment

Anushka Tiwari* and Komal Ojha

¹Department of Resource Management and Consumer Sciences
MPUAT, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

²Department of Food Science and Nutrition
MPUAT, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

Email: komalojha19.csa@gmail.com

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Introduction

Organic farming is aims at the human welfare without any harm to the environment which is the foundation of human life itself. It is the production of crops and livestock without the use of chemicals and in-organic fertilizers.

What is organic farming- Organic farming is that new technique of growing crops, in which instead of using chemical fertilizers and pesticides, organic manure, green manure, dung manure, dung gas manure, earthworm manure is used. This new

method of farming is called "organic Farming".

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Importance and Benefits of organic farming

India is considered to be an agricultural country. The history of agricultural tradition in India is very old. And 70% of the people of this country are dependent on agriculture for their livelihood. Organic Organic farming improves the quality of the land. Due to the use of chemical fertilizers, the land is moving towards barrenness. With organic fertilizers, the elements lacking in it are fulfilled and its quality can be increased to an unprecedented extent.

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There are many benefits of organic farming

- The use of organic fertilizers and organic pesticides increases the fertility of the soil.
- Irrigation costs are low in organic farming because organic fertilizers retain moisture in the soil for a long time, due to which the need for irrigation is less than that of chemical farming.
- Farmer's cost of cultivation is reduced by about 80% as compared to chemical

farming. These days the prices of chemical fertilizers are skyrocketing, organic fertilizers are prepared at very cheap prices.

- The use of chemical fertilizers destroys the bacteria that increase the productivity of the crop inside the soil, due to which the productivity of the crop decreases, that productivity can be achieved again by using organic manure.

Other benefits

- Irrigation requirement is less in this type of farming.
- The water holding capacity of the land also increases.
- The use of organic fertilizers keeps the environment pollution free.
- Humans and animals and birds are saved from many diseases.
- The crop yields well

- The grain grown through organic farming is of high quality, which is also good in terms of health.
- The value of grains grown by organic farming is also high, which increases the income of the farmer. That is, good profit at low cost.
- This maintains the fertility of the land. And by using organic manures, the quality of fertilizer capacity of the soil is continuously improved.

Manure for organic farming

Vermicompost Manure

Vermicompost manure plays an important role in maintaining the balance of nutrients in the crop. Vermicompost compost is made from special types of earthworms. Through these earthworms, non-useful organic botanicals are evaluated in a short period by making organic manure, its use improves the health of the soil and increases the fertility of the soil, which leads to qualitative improvement in crop production along with stability. In addition to nitrogen, phosphorus and potash, various types of micronutrients are also found in vermicompost. Vermi compost is an excellent organic fertilizer rich in nutritional substances. It is made by decomposing vegetation and food waste etc. by insects like earthworm etc.

Vermi-compost does not have bad smell, does not breed flies and mosquitoes and does not pollute the environment. By controlling the temperature, the bacteria

Conclusion

Organic farming improves soil fertility and yielded quality production. With the addition of compost prepared from wastes i.e., neem-cake, vermicompost, FYM etc. helps maintain organic matter in

remain active and active. Vermi-compost gets ready within one and a half to two months. It contains 2.5 to 3% nitrogen, 1.5 to 2% sulfur and 1.5 to 2% potash.

Green manure

Green-manure is called that auxiliary crop, which is mainly cultivated for the purpose of increasing the nutrients in the land and supplying organic matter in it. Often this type of crop is mixed in the soil by ploughing it only in its green state. Green manure increases the fertility of the land and protects the land. Due to continuous exploitation of soil, the essential elements for the growth of the plant present in it are getting destroyed. To compensate for these and to maintain the fertile power of the soil, green manure is a good option. When green plants (pulses and other crops or their parts) are pressed in the field to increase the amount of nitrogen or biomass of the soil, then this process is called green manure.

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